

This paper is published at Information Sciences

DOI: 10.1016/j.ins.2013.01.017

Didandeh Arman, [Bahram Sadeghi Bigham](#), Khosravian Mehdi, Farshad Bakhshandegan Moghaddam (2013)

Using Voronoi diagrams to solve a hybrid facility location problem with attentive facilities

Abstract: In this paper, we introduce a novel class of facility location problems, and propose solutions based on Voronoi diagrams. Our solutions locate a set of facilities on a two dimensional space, with respect to a set of dynamic demand. The information about these demand is gathered through modifications of the overall system, into a central decision unit. This influences our objective of minimizing the total loss function. Considering a continuous space and discrete time, facilities are assigned to meet demands in each time cycle. Two distinct approaches are proposed and thoroughly studied, followed by a case study. We call our main algorithm Reactive Agent Dynamic Voronoi Diagram Facility Spread. We also test our solutions empirically through a set of experiments. Considering n and p to be the number of demand points, and the number of facilities in hand, respectively, the time complexity of the algorithm is $O(c \cdot n^2 \cdot p \cdot \log n \cdot P)$ for a complete run of c cycles.

Keywords: Facility location, oronoi diagram, Reactive agent, omputational geometry, rtificial intelligence, Algorithm

Current Position

- Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran.
- Consultant of Mirab company in the fields of Business Intelligence (BI), Continuous Improvement and Mechatronics

Contact Info

Tel. No: +982185693007 **Cell Phone:** +989122187384

Postal Address: Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Mathematic Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran.

E-mail: [b_sadeghi_b \[@ \] alzahra.ac.ir](mailto:b_sadeghi_b@alzahra.ac.ir) Second email: [b.sadeghi.b \[@ \] gmail.com](mailto:b.sadeghi.b [@] gmail.com)

Academic Webpage: <https://staff.alzahra.ac.ir/sadeghibigham/en/>

Google scholar: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=Lvgi_zoAAAAJ&hl=en

Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=57866199500>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3387-3193>

ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Bahram_Bigham

Web Of Science: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/2009928>

Mendeley: <https://www.mendeley.com/reference-manager/library/all-references/>